

Terrestrial 5G and Starlink NTN Multi-Connectivity towards 6G Communications Integration Era: An Empirical Assessment

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ABSTRACT 5G networks have become the leading cellular connectivity standard with significant market penetration and widespread mobile infrastructure deployment. However, connectivity can degrade at cell edges even under optimal deployment conditions and high infrastructure density. This is not admissible in critical mobile applications with high-reliability requirements, e.g., autonomous driving. Integration of terrestrial 5G networks with satellite networks, referred to as multi-connectivity, emerges as an opportunity to improve performance and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) in vehicular connectivity conditions. Therefore, this paper evaluates, empirically, cellular and satellite connectivity in high-mobility scenarios over 5G and Starlink networks, jointly considering latency and throughput KPIs impacting user experience at the network layer and signal quality at the physical layer. The empirical assessment demonstrates the benefit in terms of performance when applying multi-connectivity techniques, highlighting the strong correlation between signal quality and user equipment location within the terrestrial cell. These findings pave the way for selective packet duplication by predicting when and how multi-connectivity strategies should be employed, thus resulting in several packet duplication strategies.

INDEX TERMS 5G networks, age of information, latency, satellite networks, multi-connectivity, throughput, vehicular.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the latter half of the last decade, new standards such as IMT-2020 [1], [2] from the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), or Release 15 [3], [4] from the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), laid the foundation stones for the development of 5G cellular communications [5]. Nearly a decade later, commercial deployments of 5G networks are a reality [6], [7]. Although they have improved the performance of previous cellular network technologies, e.g., LTE, performance remains far from what was anticipated and several open challenges need to be addressed [8]–[10]. While each new generation has brought significant advancements in several areas, such as modulation, coding, MIMO, bandwidth, and multiple access techniques, these advances are approaching their theoretical limit [11], [12].

Consequently, channel efficiency from a signal processing perspective has plateaued, since new specifications are not sufficient to substantially improve Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) metrics such as bitrate, latency, or error rates. On the other hand, cellular network densification has experienced slow linear growth, relying heavily on the existing base station (BS) masts from previous cellular network technology (2G, 3G, 4G) [13]. As a result, these factors have contributed to a leveling off in the improvement of KPIs. While this issue has been partially addressed in the downlink channel by increasing the Effective Isotropic Radiated Power (EIRP), which can improve the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) enhancing the downlink throughput, the uplink has been particularly affected, with no major channel improvement in 5G communications due to the limitation of the transmitted

Fig. 1. Illustration of the integration between 5G terrestrial networks and non-terrestrial satellite networks. Non-terrestrial networks can be utilized in areas where connectivity via terrestrial 5G networks is limited. This integration can be achieved through several multi-connectivity techniques, such as full duplication, selective duplication, or dynamic routing. Cell sizes for terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks are not to scale.

power on the user’s side. Thus, one of the paths toward the 6G communications era involves network densification through new communications systems beyond traditional cellular network technology communications, such as the integration of terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks (TN-NTN).

Given the previous challenges, mainly due to lack of ubiquitous coverage, the industry has shifted the focus, considering that terrestrial networks may not provide a definitive solution for achieving global coverage. Therefore, non-terrestrial networks have achieved some prominence in recent years [14]. For instance, satellite networks in low Earth orbits (LEO) have gained attention recently due to the deployment of multiple constellations such as Telesat, OneWeb and SpaceX [15]. Among the main advantages of satellite networks, over purely terrestrial networks, is the ability to provide ubiquitous coverage if a Line-of-Sight (LoS) link is established towards the sky, and the independence from dense terrestrial infrastructure [16]. These features facilitate Internet access in rural and remote areas, as well as zones such as oceans where terrestrial solutions cannot be deployed. On the other hand, satellite networks have some limitations, such as high deployment costs and limited bandwidth compared to terrestrial 5G networks. Consequently, non-terrestrial networks should be regarded as a complementary solution rather than a replacement for conventional terrestrial networks. In line with this perspective, the development of future 6G communication systems is focused on the seamless integration and operation of both

terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks [17]. Ongoing work is in progress in this area through regulatory bodies such as 3GPP, which are developing frameworks for network integration [18], [19]. This integration creates opportunities to provide and deploy more robust and reliable networks, capable of meeting requirements that neither 5G nor satellite networks could fulfill independently. An illustration of the integration between 5G and satellite networks is shown in Fig. 1, where the coverage areas of each network are highlighted. Conceptually, 5G networks generally support a higher user density due to the available bandwidth and the cell isolation principle, while the coverage area is constrained by the physical environment surrounding the base station. Therefore, the satellite network can serve as a backup during 5G network interruptions or when in limited coverage areas. This approach is expected to enable use cases such as autonomous driving, edge computing, AI offloading, remote control, reliable low-latency communications, or emergency communication systems [20]–[23]. These practical scenarios highlight the multi-connectivity potential to support and enable highly reliable and seamless connectivity for such services and mission-critical applications in vehicular connectivity conditions. Therefore, this approach envisions the joint use of terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks as an opportunity for the integrated development of future communications in the 6G era.

This paper provides an empirical assessment of terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks to evaluate the performance and improvements provided through their integration. To this

end, the study considers a comparison between the performance of multi-connectivity strategies in static and high-mobility conditions, the latter being of special interest for the deployment of future mobile communications. Additionally, a joint analysis is carried out from the perspectives of user experience in the network layer, i.e., network KPIs such as latency and throughput, and cellular signal quality in the physical plane i.e., radio KPIs such as RSRP and SNR. This relationship between both planes is fundamental since satellite networks must primarily be considered as a backup in areas prone to suffer cellular coverage outage, requiring accurate criteria to activate the non-terrestrial link effectively. For this purpose, the correlation between user experience and signal quality in the terrestrial network is analyzed, determining up to three possible multi-connectivity strategies: (i) full duplication, (ii) dynamic routing, and (iii) selective duplication, based on a trade-off between network performance and resource efficiency to meet different operational needs. Regarding the state-of-the-art, existing studies predominantly have a theoretical/simulation focus [24]–[29], while the few practical approaches are developed in static or low-speed environments, and focus solely on the user experience point of view [30]–[33]. Therefore, the main contributions of this work are:

- (i) Development of a measurement campaign in high-mobility conditions on a highway to evaluate coverage solutions based on 5G and satellite networks, and their integration through a multi-connectivity approach. In addition, baseline measurements under static conditions are included for comparison.
- (ii) Analysis of the cellular signal strength throughout the campaign to determine the impact of the position in the cell within the 5G network under mobility conditions.
- (iii) Evaluation of the network layer KPIs directly involved in the user experience (latency and throughput) in mobility conditions and how multi-connectivity influences performance.
- (iv) Assessment of the correlation between the cellular signal strength, i.e., radio KPIs, and the network KPIs to identify the optimal handover instants in the network.
- (v) Analysis of the Age of Information (AoI) in single-connectivity and multi-connectivity conditions. This metric is of particular relevance for emerging communications systems with high-reliability requirements such as those use cases previously presented.
- (vi) Proposal of several multi-connectivity strategies based on optimizing network performance (full duplication), optimizing resource allocation (dynamic routing), or a balanced solution (selective duplication) in the context of terrestrial and non-terrestrial network integration.

The previous contributions, based on a real-world empirical assessment of terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks, aim to shed light on the development of integration between cellular and satellite technologies from a practical perspective, facilitating the joint deployment of these technologies in

future communications systems. Therefore, the work offers practical insights into the performance of multi-connectivity in real conditions, which can be useful for academic researchers and engineers when optimizing deployment strategies in hybrid terrestrial and non-terrestrial systems.

The document is organized as follows. Section II presents the mobility campaign on a highway and the assembled measurement setup. Section III introduces three multi-connectivity strategies for integration of terrestrial and non-terrestrial communication technologies. Section IV analyzes the signal strength in the cellular network and the effect of cell edge. Sections V and VI analyze latency and throughput KPIs in terrestrial and non-terrestrial networks, respectively, and their correlation with radio KPI parameters in the terrestrial network. Section VII compares several strategies for multi-connectivity integration based on insights extracted throughout the work. Finally, Section VIII draws the conclusions of this study.

II. HIGH-MOBILITY MEASUREMENT CAMPAIGN

A. Test Scenario

This study has conducted a measurement campaign under high-mobility conditions. To achieve this, a route between the cities of Aalborg and Aarhus in Denmark was driven by car along a highway. This route, with a length of approximately 110 km, was driven several times at a constant speed of around 80 km/h to evaluate coverage across different connectivity technologies available on the highway. In total, time traces were measured over 7 hours, covering a total distance of approximately 550 km. These traces include information on vehicle location, cellular network signal quality parameters (RSRP and SNR), as well as latency and throughput KPIs. The route is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Covered route along the highway between the cities of Aalborg and Aarhus in Denmark. The route covers a total of 110 km. The average driving speed was 80 km/h. The location of the static analysis is indicated by a red star (Aalborg).

Regarding road conditions, the highway has two lanes in each direction with no obstructions, allowing a clear Line-of-Sight to satellite constellations deployed in low Earth orbits. The route varies gradually in elevation from 10 m to 85 m above sea level. This fact implies favorable conditions from a radio propagation perspective. Due to road being the main artery across the Jutland peninsula, mobile network operators have deployed base stations along the highway with interdistances ranging from approximately 3 km to 6 km. This deployment is publicly available through the Danish Agency for Digital Government [13]. According to the agency, the scenario under study does not present satellite network congestion issues, as the number of subscriptions in the region is relatively low.

As a baseline for comparison, a second measurement location was chosen on the rooftop of a building at Aalborg University (AAU), located in a semi-urban area on the outskirts of the city of Aalborg. This location has an obstructed LoS (OLoS) to a cellular base station, located within a range of 200 m, and an unobstructed LoS to the satellite network. This static location, depicted in Fig. 2 and where time traces have been recorded for approximately 3 hours, is used to compare static versus dynamic connectivity conditions.

B. Measurement Setup

To enable an integrated evaluation of cellular and satellite networks, a compact hardware solution is required to facilitate simultaneous assessment of both solutions. For this purpose, we utilize the multi-access gateway (MAGW) Newport GW6400, connected to a 5G SIM8380G-M2 modem. This modem, despite supporting multiple frequency bands, was manually configured to operate in the sub-6 GHz 5G bands, ensuring connectivity to a 5G network when available. The MAGW includes inputs for supplementary interfaces, enabling integration with a satellite network via Ethernet or with GPS data through a coaxial connection. For 5G cellular connectivity, the network of one of Denmark’s leading mobile operators was employed, while satellite connectivity was provided by the LEO Starlink satellite constellation [34]. A schematic of the measurement setup can be seen in Fig. 3(a). Given the availability of both terrestrial and non-terrestrial network interfaces in the MAGW, packet forwarding is synchronized at the application layer to assess the performance in both single-connectivity and multi-connectivity modes (see discussion in Section III). This is possible since packets being forwarded are time-aligned, facilitating simultaneous and comparable values for network KPIs (latency and throughput). The equipment is mounted on the roof of a vehicle to enable operation under mobile conditions. A photograph of the assembled setup is presented in Fig. 3(b).

Regarding the radio KPIs captured by this hardware: (i) RSRP and SNR are periodically recorded via the synchronization signal block (SSB) transmitted by BSs; (ii) latitude and longitude are obtained from the GPS satellite constellation. Concerning the network KPIs: (iii) latency data is acquired using the *ping* tool, which measures the Round-Trip Time (RTT) to the MAGW; and (iv) throughput data is obtained via the *iperf3* tool, which calculates downlink/uplink throughput over the past 1-second interval from the received/sent 1500 Bytes UDP packets in that interval. The server for latency and throughput tests is physically located at Aalborg University. Details concerning the *ping* periodicity and *iperf3* target throughput of each test are presented in Sections V and VI.

Fig. 3. (a) Schematic of the measurement setup and interconnection of the equipment, and (b) photograph of the equipment assembly on the car roof. In the photograph, the battery and the Starlink router are located inside the vehicle.

III. MULTI-CONNECTIVITY STRATEGIES

According to the setup presented in Section II, in which cellular and satellite interfaces are available, as well as the radio KPIs of the 5G network, it is possible to determine several smart packet duplication strategies for the multi-connectivity mode. In particular, the choice of one strategy or another is based on a trade-off between prioritizing (i) better performance, (ii) resource usage, or (iii) balancing performance and resource usage. Therefore, the following strategies can be defined:

- (i) **Full duplication:** This strategy prioritizes maximum performance by duplicating packets from both interfaces in the network at all times, regardless of radio

Fig. 4. Conceptual system model for full duplication, selective duplication and dynamic routing strategies.

KPIs quality, thus ensuring the best performance among the available cellular and satellite interfaces.

- (ii) **Dynamic routing:** In this strategy, a single active interface is maintained at a certain time, prioritizing efficiency in terms of resource allocation. For this purpose, the cellular interface is used unless one of the radio KPIs (SNR/RSRP) degrades below a threshold, at which point network traffic is routed through the backup satellite interface.
- (iii) **Selective duplication:** This strategy is similar to dynamic routing, activating the satellite interface only when the radio KPIs degrade below a threshold value. The main difference is that when the satellite link is activated, packets continue to be routed through the cellular network, thus duplicating packets selectively in time.

An overview of the main benefits and drawbacks is illustrated in Table 1, which shows the trade-offs involved among the three multi-connectivity strategies.

Fig. 4 shows a conceptual multi-connectivity system model, focusing on the user equipment (UE) multi-access connections. Solid lines indicate logically active connections in which resources are actively allocated for data transmission, whereas dashed lines indicate resource allocation subject to radio KPI conditions. For all connections, control plane signaling is maintained to keep the connection context.

At the UE, data from the application layer is duplicated via different network layer interfaces for transmission over the terrestrial and/or non-terrestrial radio access network. In implementation, since multi-connectivity should be transparent to the application, the duplication is carried out at the network layer by encapsulating network layer (IP) packets with unique identifiers associated with the available interfaces. Practical implementations of this model have been experimentally developed and validated at Aalborg University, and are available as open-source tools [35], [36]. Note that in practical implementation, with packets duplicated at the network layer, those encapsulated packets whose unique identifiers have already been received through a different interface will be discarded, preventing simultaneous evaluation of the three strategies under the exact same conditions. Therefore, in this work, the duplication has been performed at the application layer. From own tests, we have confirmed that this has only minimal impact to performance.

To quantitatively perform an analysis of the efficiency of each strategy, it is possible to estimate the additional network load incurred by each strategy in the backup network, i.e. the satellite network. The network load incurred by each strategy in the satellite network is calculated as follows:

$$BW_{\text{usage (DL/UL)}} = \frac{Sat_{\text{usage}} \cdot TP_{\text{target (DL/UL)}} (Mbps)}{TP_{\text{sustained (DL/UL)}} (Mbps)}, \quad (1)$$

where Sat_{usage} is the satellite link usage in the range [0, 1], $TP_{\text{target (DL/UL)}}$ is the targeted throughput given an user employing multi-connectivity strategies, and $TP_{\text{sustained (DL/UL)}}$ stands for satellite beam achievable sustained throughput.

The full duplication strategy, as well as the relation between radio and network KPIs, are explored in Sections IV, V and VI. Based on the insights from these sections, Section VII presents results for selective duplication and dynamic routing and compares the strategies to determine the benefits and drawbacks of each one based on the performance and efficiency trade-off.

IV. TEST SCENARIO ANALYSIS

In the proposed scenario, the BS deployment follows a linear configuration, which sequentially covers different sections of the highway with a BS spacing of approximately 3 km to 6 km. This arrangement typically results in only one optimal

TABLE 1. Trade-off involved among multi-connectivity duplication strategies.

	← Performance		Efficiency →
	Full Duplication	Selective Duplication	Dynamic Routing
Pros	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highest reliability and robustness - Ensures lowest latency achievable - Ideal for mission-critical applications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Balanced trade-off between reliability and efficiency - Reduced bandwidth usage compared to full duplication - Adaptive mechanism optimizes network usage based on correlation between radio and network layers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Most bandwidth-efficient approach - Lowest transmission overhead - Reduced energy consumption
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High bandwidth consumption - Increased network congestion and overhead - Higher energy consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Still incurs overhead when duplication is triggered - Less reliable than full duplication - Requires real-time monitoring of radio KPIs and high correlation with the network KPIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lower reliability and robustness - Requires real-time monitoring of radio KPIs and high correlation with the network KPIs

Fig. 5. RSRP and SNR distributions: (a) empirical distribution function for measurement campaigns in mobility and static conditions, (b) temporal variation under mobility conditions, and (c) RSRP and SNR for the driven route given the GPS coordinates. For visualization purposes, a 10-second moving average has been applied¹.

BS available within the coverage of the user, generally the BS closest to the user equipment. This contrasts with densely populated urban areas, where multiple BSs may serve as backups in a given location. Consequently, this network configuration causes the user to move between the center and edge of a cell in the cellular network. Under these conditions, it is reasonable to expect that the user will experience optimal signal levels near the cell center, with signal quality deteriorating as the user approaches the cell edge. According to the European Commission’s Digital

Decade Country Report 2024 [37], Denmark is one of the top EU countries in terms of 5G connectivity deployment. As a result, this study is conducted in a highly favorable setting where a single-connectivity 5G solution should perform efficiently. Demonstrating the benefits of multi-connectivity under such conditions would suggest that these advantages would be even more significant in less favorable and more challenging environments.

According to the 5G network deployment along the route to which the user is connected, approximately 30 BSs are available, primarily operating in the 700 MHz band. To characterize the signal quality, the empirical distribution function (EDF) is calculated for RSRP and SNR levels along the route. For reference, these distributions are compared with the EDF for the static scenario. The results are presented in Fig. 5(a). Focusing on the 10th and 90th percentiles of the RSRP along the highway, the received signal varies from -68.5 dBm to -97.4 dBm , indicating a variability range of up to 28.9 dB . In contrast, under static conditions, this signal fluctuates only between -82.9 dBm and -87.3 dBm , with variability of just 4.4 dB , which supports the effect of mobility on the signal strength due to the conditions at cell center and cell edge. For the SNR, the 10th to 90th percentile range in the mobility scenario is 18.6 dB , while in the static scenario this range is 6.0 dB .

To understand the temporal correlation of the signal levels, Fig. 5(b) presents a time trace of the complete 110 km route previously depicted in Fig. 2. Note that both parameters exhibit constant fluctuations, characterized by upward and downward trends. Upon closer examination of the peak distribution, these peaks occur at regular intervals ranging from 150 s to 300 s. Given the constant vehicle speed of 80 km/h along the route, this behavior suggests a BS periodicity between 3.3 km and 6.7 km in terms of distance, which aligns with the approximate distance of the cellular cells deployed along the highway. Thus, the temporal relationship corroborates the strong dependence of signal levels on cell position in the test scenario. Finally, Fig. 5(c) illustrates these signal levels along the route based on the recorded GPS position. Similar to Fig. 5(b), periodical increases and decreases in signal levels with respect to vehicle location and BS position along the route are observed.

Previous observations of signal levels at cell edges suggest that user experience may be impacted in these regions, even in scenarios that appear to be well-covered. Therefore, the following sections analyze the correlation between user experience, represented by KPIs such as latency and throughput, and received signal levels from a radio propagation perspective. Given the extensive coverage provided by satellite network constellations, multi-connectivity at terrestrial cell edges can be beneficial to mitigate potential loss of cellular

¹GPS and temporal traces require spatial and temporal averaging due to the large number of data to be displayed on short temporal [Fig. 5(b)] and spatial [Fig. 5(c) and Fig. 6] axes. The probability distributions presented throughout the paper do show the raw data without any moving average.

Fig. 6. Round-Trip Time measured on the highway under mobility conditions for 5G and satellite connectivity. For visualization purposes, a 10-second moving average has been applied¹. Yellow colors indicate that the RTT might be 150 ms or higher.

coverage in specific locations. It is worth noting that the coverage range of a satellite cell is significantly larger than that of a 5G cell [38], and suggests the feasibility of using LEO satellite networks as a backup for 5G cellular networks.

V. LATENCY CONNECTIVITY ASSESMENT

As described in Section II.B, the *ping* tool, which establishes the RTT between the user equipment, i.e. the MAGW, and a server located at Aalborg University are used for latency analysis in the network. To enable continuous monitoring, latency is measured every 100 ms along the route. These measurements are conducted individually on each interface, terrestrial (5G) and non-terrestrial (Starlink), and are time-aligned to determine the optimal connectivity solution at each instant. Fig. 6 presents the evaluation of this latency throughout the highway for both 5G and satellite connectivity. The results show that the 5G network can maintain latency values around 25 ms with high probability, with some few high-latency spikes. The satellite network exhibits higher average RTT values, approximately 60 ms, with variability between 50 ms and 90 ms. Despite this higher average latency, the satellite connection demonstrates larger stability, avoiding the RTT spikes observed in the 5G cellular network. These findings suggest that, while the 5G network generally offers superior latency performance, it experiences intermittent coverage gaps, likely when the user equipment is at the cell edge according to the GPS traces. Meanwhile, the satellite network, despite its higher average latency, provides more stable connectivity by minimizing latency spikes along the route. Approximately 30 handovers occur within the cellular network according to the BSs available along the route (see Section IV).

To assess the influence of mobility on connectivity with both networks, a comparison is made with the static scenario. Fig. 7 and Table 2 present the RTT complementary empirical distribution function (CEDF) for the 5G and satellite networks under static and mobility conditions, and latency statistics for several reliability thresholds, respec-

Fig. 7. Latency complementary cumulative distribution function for cellular, satellite, and full duplication multi-connectivity under static (solid lines) and mobility conditions (dashed lines).

TABLE 2. Latency statistics for 5G, Starlink and multi-connectivity technologies for static and mobility scenarios

Rel.	Cellular (5G)		Satellite (Starlink)		Multi-Connectivity	
	Static	Mobility	Static	Mobility	Static	Mobility
10^{-1}	39 ms	33 ms	87 ms	83 ms	39 ms	33 ms
10^{-2}	60 ms	57 ms	127 ms	131 ms	52 ms	50 ms
10^{-3}	83 ms	>500 ms	163 ms	218 ms	70 ms	73 ms
10^{-4}	254 ms	>500 ms	196 ms	427 ms	86 ms	109 ms

tively. The CEDF can be divided into two regions: (i) the high-probability upper region ($> 10^{-2}$), and (ii) the low-probability lower region ($< 10^{-2}$). In the high-probability region, 5G connectivity clearly outperforms Starlink, with lower latency values. Furthermore, no significant differences are observed between static and mobility conditions, showing similar trends across both cases (see Fig. 7 for Rel. $> 10^{-2}$). However, substantial differences emerge between static and mobility scenarios in the low-probability region, as the tails of the distribution rise notably in the mobility cases. The crossover point around 180 ms between the 5G and Starlink curves in the low-probability regime is noteworthy, indicating that Starlink provides larger reliability in terms of latency by capping maximum values and avoiding the spikes shown previously in Fig. 6 for the terrestrial network. The increased latency in the 5G network under mobility conditions may be attributed to cell-edge effects, as previously predicted in Fig. 5(a) according to radio KPIs values, and will be further analyzed in this section by examining the correlation between RSRP/SNR and latency. For the satellite network under mobility, maximum latency values around 450 ms are observed. Along the route, highway overpasses occasionally obstruct the LoS, blocking it for approximately 10 to 12 m. Given the driving speed of 80 km/h, the LoS between the UE and Starlink is obstructed for about 0.5 s, which would account for the observed latency increase. Overall, the distribution of latency tails in the CEDF indicates that mobility primarily impacts the performance of the cellular network.

For several applications with severe low latency requirements [39], the latency performance observed in the cellular network might not be sufficient to support such use cases. For this reason, latency analysis from a multi-connectivity perspective is proposed. The multi-connectivity paradigm explores whether it is possible to improve network performance by integrating multiple technologies, such as 5G and LEO satellite networks. Due to the time-aligned requests on both interfaces, it is possible to determine the network performance under multi-connectivity conditions, assuming that the latency in the network will be the minimum between the terrestrial and satellite networks at any given time. Fig. 7 shows the CEDF of the RTT for the multi-connectivity scenario in static and dynamic conditions. Taking advantage of the minimum latency across both connectivity options, latency values below 110 ms are achieved in 99.99% of the cases. Note that in the high probability region, the multi-connectivity curve replicates the behavior of the 5G network, as most of the time this turns out to be the optimal connectivity option. However, in the low probability region, this curve is significantly below the single-connectivity cases, which is due to the use of the satellite network when the cellular network no longer provides the lowest latency values. Even the multi-connectivity case under mobility conditions improves the single-connectivity curves for both 5G and satellite connectivity. One reason for the noticeable improvement in the tails might be the decorrelation between the two networks, which suggests that performance in one network is independent of the other.

In summary, these results highlight the benefit brought by network integration through multi-connectivity, as the 5G optimal latency performance with low latencies is achieved, while the high reliability of Starlink is maintained in the bounded tails of the CEDF. The multi-connectivity case presented always make use of both cellular and satellite interfaces, i.e., a full duplication strategy. This strategy is the most robust in terms of performance, as it ensures that the lowest latency will always be achieved between both available interfaces. However, this is not the optimal solution in terms of resource allocation, since the resources of one of the interfaces will always be discarded. The study of other multi-connectivity strategies that balance the performance of the KPIs against resource allocation are further explored in Section VII. To perform this analysis it is necessary to determine in a preliminary step whether there is a correlation between the physical layer signal strength in the cellular network (RSRP/SNR), and the user network experienced KPIs, i.e. latency and throughput. If such correlation exists, it would be possible to determine when it is necessary to enable the satellite interface.

Fig. 8 shows the relation between the RSRP/SNR of the 5G terrestrial network and the RTT experienced by the user. These distributions present samples with latency below 100 ms, accounting for 99.51% of the acquired samples. These latency values are grouped into ranges of

Fig. 8. Empirical distribution of RTT latency values in the 5G cellular network under mobility conditions for several ranges of (a) RSRP and (b) SNR. Lower RSRP and SNR values indicate an increase in the probability of high latencies.

possible values for the RSRP and SNR. It is observed that for high values of both RSRP and SNR, the latency is bounded in the low latency range. However, the likelihood of larger latency increases as the signal strength or SNR is reduced. Note that the entire latency distribution does not uniformly shift as RSRP or SNR decreases, but rather a portion of the samples are shifted to larger latencies. For low RSRP/SNR conditions, the probability distributions show several peaks, indicating that the latency values tends to cluster in particular intervals. For instance, this is observed in the SNR range $[-7.5, 0]$ dB. This pattern suggests that each peak in the probability distribution corresponds to retransmissions induced by poor network coverage due to low signal strength. In brief, this analysis shows that high SNR values ensure low latency values. Low SNR values can also achieve low latency, but the likelihood of higher values increases significantly. As previously depicted in Fig. 5, these low SNR values are related to the cell edge in the cellular network, which demonstrates the difficulties of ensuring with high probability a low latency value at the cell edge, having a remarkable influence on the user experience when low latency requirements are needed.

Fig. 9. Downlink throughput EDF for cellular and satellite connectivity under static (solid lines) and mobility (dashed lines) conditions given (a) high throughput tests (100 Mbps) and (b) stability tests (10 Mbps). Full duplication performance is also shown for the stability tests.

VI. THROUGHPUT CONNECTIVITY ASSESSMENT

This section presents an analysis of uplink and downlink throughput for 5G and Starlink. Both static and mobility cases are also considered to assess the impact of both conditions. For the evaluation of connectivity, the *iperf3* tool is configured as a client from the MAGW, with the server residing at Aalborg University. A UDP connection is used to measure the throughput averaged over 1 second intervals for both uplink and downlink. Taking into account different user requirements, two types of tests are performed: (i) high throughput tests and (ii) stability tests. In the first one, a target throughput of 100 Mbps DL/30 Mbps UL is requested according to the values established by the Danish Agency for Digital Government for broadband access [13]. These targets allow users to access high-bandwidth services such as video streaming, where broadband resources are more critical than instantaneous connectivity, as brief interruptions can be mitigated by buffering mechanisms. These high capacity tests are carried out by measuring downlink and uplink throughput for 30 minutes each along the route. In the second type of tests, a throughput of 10 Mbps DL/10 Mbps UL is requested to support use cases that require low-capacity but yet a stable link over time. Therefore, these stability tests evaluate use

Fig. 10. Empirical distribution of downlink throughput values for the stability tests in the 5G cellular network under mobility conditions for several ranges of (a) RSRP and (b) SNR. Lower RSRP and SNR values indicate an increase in the probability of low throughput.

cases that need to satisfy a continuous flow of data over long periods of time. They are performed by measuring downlink and uplink throughput for 90 minutes each along the route.

Fig. 9(a) shows the EDF of the high throughput downlink tests for 5G and Starlink under both static and mobility conditions. In the static scenario, both technologies continuously satisfy the 100 Mbps demand, with 5G being slightly better in the low probability region. In the worst-case scenario, Starlink maintains at least 55 Mbps, while the 5G case achieves a minimum of 75 Mbps. In the mobility scenario, the similarities between the Starlink curves and the differences between the 5G curves are worth noting. In particular, the Starlink EDF performs very similar to the static case. This fact can be explained from two perspectives: (i) from the user mobility perspective, in which the speed of the car is low relative to the high orbital speeds in LEO satellites, and therefore the impact of the vehicle motion is minimal in terms of connectivity; (ii) the satellite beam coverage area is large enough so that the variability of the signal level is not significant [38], thus avoiding abrupt drops in the throughput experienced by the user. Distribution tails are slightly worse compared to static conditions, which can

be attributed to the overpasses found along the highway where the LoS is obstructed for approximately half a second.

In contrast, the performance of the 5G network under mobility changes completely compared to the static scenario. Specifically, while 5G meets target throughput in almost 100% of the static cases, mobility conditions decrease throughput to half (54.9 Mbps) in the worst 20% of the cases and below 36.9 Mbps in the worst 10% of the cases. As previously discussed, this could be attributed to signal strength variability due to the car motion between the center and the cell edge. These results yield that in static conditions the 5G network appears sufficient to meet high throughput demands, while in mobility the signal level degradation in 5G makes Starlink more reliable as it maintains consistent performance regardless of movement.

A similar analysis is performed for the stability tests, as shown in Fig. 9(b), which presents the downlink throughput EDF given a target throughput of 10 Mbps sustained over 90 minutes. In this case, the aim is to verify that the connectivity is stable for the entire period of time, while ensuring the 10 Mbps target throughput. For the static scenario, a minimum throughput of 9 Mbps is always obtained in both technologies. However, under mobility conditions, it is observed that throughput drops below 6 Mbps for 99% reliability on both technologies, reaching null values, i.e. service interruption, around 0.1% and 0.01% of time. As discussed in Fig. 5(a), in the case of the 5G network it is due to the low signal level at the cell edge, while in the case of Starlink it is due to temporary blockage of the LoS. These results highlight that, under mobility, minimum throughput requirements may not be met. As in Section V, Fig. 9(b) illustrates the throughput performance under a multi-connectivity strategy with full duplication. The EDF curve for multi-connectivity in mobility denotes that it is possible to achieve performance similar to that of 5G and Starlink in single-connectivity in the static case. The minimum throughput found over 90 minutes is 8 Mbps, which demonstrates that this strategy can provide a stable seamless connectivity service even under challenging conditions such as the high mobility scenario presented.

Following the same procedure outlined in Section V, Figs. 10(a) and 10(b) present the relation between signal strength and SNR concerning downlink throughput for the stability tests conducted along the driven route. Regarding the relation for signal strength, $RSRP > -65$ dBm reliably meets the target throughput. However, for $RSRP < -65$ dBm, the relation becomes less consistent. That is why the correlation with SNR is taken into account [see Fig. 10(b)]. In this case, it is observed that all throughput tests carried out in Fig. 10(b) with $SNR > 15$ dB ensure the 10 Mbps target. As the SNR value decreases, an increasing number of samples fall short of this target. In fact, samples approaching 0 Mbps, i.e., no connectivity, are progressively observed as SNR decreases. This pattern is very similar to that observed in the latency study, where

high SNR values ensure that the target throughput is met. On the contrary, low SNR values do not guarantee low throughput but the likelihood of lower values increases significantly.

Focusing on the uplink, tests similar to those performed for the downlink are carried out. Fig. 11(a) shows the uplink throughput measured for a target of 30 Mbps, which according to the Danish Agency for Digital Government is sufficient to support broadband services in uplink [13]. In the static scenario, 5G is able to provide a stable connection of around 30 Mbps most of the time. However, this is not the case for Starlink connectivity in the static scenario where throughput ranges between 10 Mbps and 30 Mbps. This contrasts with the downlink, where Starlink was able to consistently provide 100 Mbps. This difference might be due to the link budget, as the transmission power and antenna gain on both Starlink ground stations and orbiting satellites are higher than that of the user terminal equipment [38]. Therefore, the transmitted power constrains the link between the user terminal and the satellite, resulting in a noticeable decrease in throughput. In the mobility scenario, the throughput in Starlink is very similar to the static case, which is to be expected due to the mobility of the vehicle relative to LEO satellites. Regarding 5G in the mobility scenario, however, some degradation is observed with throughput falling below 30 Mbps in 50% of cases, an effect that was also found in mobility for 5G in downlink [see Fig. 9(a)]. While in downlink Starlink was consistently a better solution, in uplink 5G is a better alternative despite the degradation in the tail.

In the stability tests shown in Fig. 11(b), with a target uplink of 10 Mbps over 90 minutes, there is a similar trend for both connectivity solutions in the static case. Both solutions can provide 10 Mbps with a reliability of 90%, but this value drops to around 3 Mbps with 99.9% reliability. In other words, the connectivity is never entirely lost, but some degradation occurs in the tails. In the mobility case, the performance deteriorates further due to service interruptions with 99% reliability, i.e. close to 1% interruption probability. As explained in Fig. 11(b), these interruptions are due to LoS blockage in Starlink and poor 5G signal quality at the cell edge. However, the difference between these two factors can be exploited to improve performance through multi-connectivity. Using a full duplication strategy, minimum uplink throughput of 7.5 Mbps and 6 Mbps is found for the static and mobility scenarios, respectively. These results show that multi-connectivity can provide seamless connectivity over the journey between the cities of Aalborg and Aarhus, which is not feasible using single-connectivity approaches.

Figs. 12(a) and 12(b) present the relation of uplink throughput values with respect to signal strength and SNR, respectively. It is observed that $RSRP > -80$ dBm and $SNR > 15$ dB can consistently achieve throughput values close to the target objective. However, below these threshold

Fig. 11. Uplink throughput EDF for cellular and satellite connectivity under static (solid lines) and mobility (dashed lines) conditions given (a) high throughput tests (30 Mbps) and (b) stability tests (10 Mbps). Full duplication performance is also shown for the stability tests.

the performance decays significantly. Focusing on SNR, and in contrast to the downlink case where the throughput degradation was gradual [see Fig. 10(b)], it is observed that for $\text{SNR} < 15$ dB, samples with null throughput start to appear recurrently. This fact indicates the greater difficulty of the cellular network to provide a stable uplink service, which can also be corroborated by comparing the distribution tails in Fig. 9(b) and Fig. 11(b).

In summary, the results show the advantages of employing a multi-connectivity strategy to maximize uplink and downlink throughput. The decorrelation of coverage gaps across both networks allows multi-connectivity to benefit from channel diversity by providing downlink and uplink bandwidth of at least 8 Mbps and 6 Mbps, respectively, under mobility conditions.

VII. AGE OF INFORMATION

Age of Information is a metric that quantifies the time elapsed since the most recent update of information was received by a given entity. Formally, AoI is defined as $t - u$ at time instant t , given some data that was updated at time instant u [40]. Examples of applicability of this metric are systems with low latency requirements over long periods of

Fig. 12. Empirical distribution of uplink throughput values for the stability tests in the 5G cellular network under mobility conditions for several ranges of (a) RSRP and (b) SNR. Lower RSRP and SNR values indicate an increase in the probability of low throughput.

time, e.g., autonomous driving [41]. In this work, AoI will serve to evaluate the advantages of multi-connectivity versus single-connectivity strategies.

In particular, applied to our study, and according to Section V, the equipment used during the vehicular measurement campaign has a refresh rate of 100 ms. Assuming an approximate latency of 25 ms in the 5G network, and under optimal operating conditions, i.e., a stable connection and no network interruptions, the AoI is expected to follow a uniform distribution within the range $[25, 125)$ ms. As an example, Fig. 13 illustrates a representative time trace of the AoI. At the start of the trace, the AoI is bounded approximately between 25 ms and 125 ms. This behavior is explained by the fact that the minimum AoI is provided by the 5G network latency, with AoI increasing linearly until a new packet is received approximately 100 ms later. Note that in the single-connectivity cellular scenario, there is a case in which a new packet is not received, increasing the AoI above the expected range and indicating a potential coverage issue in the cellular network. However, for the multi-connectivity case, the satellite network available as backup successfully restore the AoI to the nominal range. Therefore, this example illustrates how multi-connectivity

Fig. 13. Illustrative temporal trace of the Age of Information. The multi-connectivity strategy enables a stable AoI, even in the presence of potential cellular coverage issues.

can mitigate high AoI values. Subsections VII.A, VII.B and VII.C discuss the impact of alternative multi-connectivity strategies on AoI and the trade-off involved among multi-connectivity duplication strategies.

A. Selective Duplication Strategy

According to Sections V and VI, there is a relation between the signal strength in the cellular network and the KPIs that affect the user experience. Therefore, this suggests that packet duplication can be applied selectively during periods when the cellular network deteriorates, e.g., at the cell edge. Given the multi-connectivity strategies defined in Section III, selective duplication can be applied. This strategy leads to network resource savings compared to a full duplication strategy, while maintaining network performance during periods of poor cellular connectivity.

Fig. 14 shows the CEDF of the AoI for the selective duplication scenario given different SNR thresholds that enable packet duplication. The CEDF curves are shown for the cases with an SNR threshold of 1 dB, 3 dB, 7 dB

Fig. 14. Age of Information complementary empirical cumulative distribution function for a selective duplication strategy given several threshold SNR values under mobility conditions. In terms of the threshold, AoI shifts from the 5G cellular single-connectivity case towards the full duplication multi-connectivity case. Satellite percentage of usage time is labeled.

and 14 dB, for which satellite connectivity usage is 15%, 24%, 46% and 78%, respectively. At an SNR threshold of 1 dB, although the tail distribution is slightly improved, AoI values > 600 ms persist. However, SNR thresholds of 3 dB limits the AoI tails below 350 ms, improving the single-connectivity satellite case and approaching the performance of a full duplication strategy. Therefore, these results suggest that with a selective duplication for only 24% of the network packets it is possible to obtain a performance comparable to the 100% duplication required in the full duplication approach. This optimized resource utilization is possible due to the high correlation between KPIs and signal strength observed in previous sections. Note also that for duplication of 78%, i.e., an SNR threshold of 14 dB, the CEDF is similar to the full duplication scenario. In addition, Table 3 shows additional SNR thresholds and the associated usage time for each technology. These results demonstrate that selective duplication opens the possibility of achieving quasi-optimal performance by taking advantage of the correlation between SNR and KPIs, requiring packet duplication only during periods of degraded SNR, thus minimizing service interruptions and resource overhead. In summary, this connectivity option can be considered when seeking a balance between performance and optimal resource management.

B. Dynamic Routing Strategy

According to Section III, a more conservative approach than selective duplication in terms of resource utilization can be achieved through dynamic routing. In this strategy, packets are never duplicated in the network, but depending on the signal quality of the cellular network the information is dynamically transmitted via the cellular network or via the satellite network. Fig. 15 shows the AoI for a dynamic routing strategy given several SNR threshold values. The AoI behavior shows two trends based on the upper and lower regions defined in the CEDF, above and

Fig. 15. Age of Information complementary empirical cumulative distribution function for a dynamic routing strategy given several threshold SNR values under mobility conditions. In terms of the threshold, AoI shifts from the 5G cellular single-connectivity towards the Starlink satellite single-connectivity. Cellular - Satellite percentage of usage time is labeled.

TABLE 3. Usage time of cellular and satellite technology for each connectivity strategy

SNR threshold	Selective Duplication		Dynamic Routing	
	Cellular (5G)	Satellite (Starlink)	Cellular (5G)	Satellite (Starlink)
0 dB	100%	11%	89%	11%
2 dB	100%	20%	80%	20%
4 dB	100%	29%	71%	29%
6 dB	100%	41%	59%	41%
8 dB	100%	52%	48%	52%
10 dB	100%	61%	39%	61%
12 dB	100%	70%	30%	70%
14 dB	100%	78%	22%	78%

below approximately 3×10^{-3} . In the upper region, since the AoI is clustered with high probability, the 5G average AoI is lower than the satellite AoI. This implies that as the threshold increases, progressively the AoI distribution shifts towards the satellite network trend. These results are expected because as the threshold increases, more reliance is given to satellite connectivity. In contrast, focusing on the lower region, representing the tails of the distribution, a different pattern is observed. For low threshold values, e.g., 1 dB, there is a non-zero probability of $\text{AoI} > 600$ ms. However, as the threshold is increased to values between 3 dB and 7 dB, an optimal balance is found, improving even the tails of the satellite single-connectivity case. Finally, if the threshold is increased too much, the CEDF converges to satellite connectivity.

These results demonstrate that dynamic routing with an optimal choice of the SNR threshold, while increasing the average AoI with respect to the cellular case (upper region), achieves superior performance over that of each single-connectivity technology considered separately (lower region). Compared to multi-connectivity strategies, this is the most efficient case in terms of resource savings since no packet duplication is required (see Table 3 for dynamic routing usage time).

C. Multi-Connectivity Strategies Comparative

Sections VII.A and VII.B have presented two alternatives to the full duplication multi-connectivity strategy. According to the previous results (see Figs. 14 and 15, and Table 1) and the discussion in Section III, the choice of the optimal strategy should be guided by the desired balance between performance and efficiency. For a resource use efficiency assessment, (1) can be applied considering the satellite link usage time shown in Table 3, and that the sustained throughput that a satellite beam can provide is approximately 420 Mbps for downlink and 21 Mbps for uplink [38]. Fig. 16(a) shows the additional network load in terms of bandwidth usage incurred in a satellite beam when applying different multi-connectivity strategies for downlink and uplink given several target throughput values. For instance, when targeting a downlink throughput of 100 Mbps, full duplication implies a use of 24% of the satellite beam bandwidth. However, for selective duplication or dynamic routing with an SNR threshold of 3 dB, this value drops to 6%, implying a reduction of 18% with respect to full duplication. On the other hand, the uplink channel exhibits a larger utilization of the available bandwidth, primarily due to its lower sustained throughput rates. Consequently, the implementation of efficient resource management strategies becomes critical in uplink scenarios. Assuming a satellite link dedicated to multi-connectivity services, the maximum number of users making simultaneous use of these services can be calculated as the number of users that would imply a bandwidth usage of 100%. This estimation is shown in Fig. 16(b). For instance, it can be seen that selective duplication and dynamic routing with a 3 dB threshold increase the number of users by a factor of four compared to full duplication.

In summary, this section has shown results related to each strategy in terms of performance and efficiency. The comparative analysis allows us to quantitatively show the advantages and disadvantages regarding network performance and resource saving for each multi-connectivity strategy. Hence,

Fig. 16. (a) Bandwidth network load incurred in a satellite beam, and (b) maximum number of simultaneous users when applying different multi-connectivity strategies for downlink and uplink given several target throughput values.

while there is no global optimal strategy, each use case must be analyzed independently to determine the optimal solution. Note that due to the empirical nature of the work, the results shown are particular to the route studied and applicable to similar connectivity environments. In scenarios with a worse cellular network deployment than the one shown in the analysis, as could be the case in predominantly rural areas, a larger dependence on the satellite link would be expected due to the lack of terrestrial coverage. On the other hand, in urban scenarios, the predominant use of 5G connectivity is expected due to the dense deployment of base stations, and the fact that these scenarios are more prone to blocking of the satellite link, which relies heavily on LoS. In addition, our satellite measurements were performed without congestion on the satellite link. In regions with larger usage of the satellite service, although satellite operators often cap the number of simultaneous users, there may be instances when the throughput provided by the satellite link is saturated. Therefore, the reported results could be affected in areas with high service demand for satellite network operators, and overall reduce the gain from multi-connectivity due to the reduced freedom in duplicating or dynamically routing packets.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented experimental results under high mobility conditions to evaluate the performance of terrestrial 5G and Starlink non-terrestrial networks. This assessment considers not only the performance of each individual network, but also the joint performance of both networks in terms of latency and throughput through multi-connectivity strategies. Additionally, signal quality parameters in the cellular network are monitored to determine the relationship between user experience based on network KPIs, i.e., throughput and latency, versus signal quality based on radio KPIs, i.e., RSRP and SNR.

Regarding the 5G network, a considerable impact of mobility on the terrestrial 5G network due to variable signal quality conditions between the cell center (SNR > 20 dB) and the cell edge (SNR < -5 dB) is observed, implying a degradation in the end-user's network KPIs. In contrast, Starlink is not similarly affected by cell coverage due to user mobility since the relative distance to the LEO satellite has less variability. For instance, 5G has superior median latency performance (24 ms) compared to Starlink (57 ms), but the likelihood of high latency values for 5G (cellular beam coverage outage) is larger, i.e., $P(\text{Lat.} < 500 \text{ ms}) < 99.9\%$ than for Starlink (satellite beam coverage outage), i.e., $P(\text{Lat.} < 500 \text{ ms}) > 99.99\%$. Therefore, looking towards future seamless communications, integrating terrestrial and non-terrestrial technologies substantially improves outage performance due to the availability of the satellite network at the 5G cell edge, e.g., $P(\text{Lat.} < 110 \text{ ms}) > 99.99\%$. The enhanced KPIs will enable reliable low-latency communications for use cases such as AI offloading and remote control.

Concerning multi-connectivity strategies, the correlation between latency and throughput with radio KPIs (SNR and RSRP) has been demonstrated. This fact allows us to choose intelligently when to perform packet duplication in the network, enabling alternative strategies to full duplication, such as selective duplication and dynamic routing. These strategies present efficient solutions from a saving resource perspective with a quasi-optimal performance.

The empirical results shown throughout this work open the door to the extensive use of multi-connectivity techniques in future communications through the integration of multiple technologies for improving reliability in communication networks. As part of future work, further measurement campaigns will assess scenarios of different nature, including rural and urban environments, to extend the applicability of the multi-connectivity strategies under different propagation and network deployment conditions. Thus, this work supports the vision of a seamless interconnected world towards 6G communications era in which the integration of multiple communication technologies (cellular TN, satellite NTN and beyond) will be fundamental to achieve enhanced levels of reliability, coverage and scalability in global networks.

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